

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MOISTURE OF THE RAINFED SOYBEAN FIELD BY THE END OF THE SEASON

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Abstract

Some of the data of 2016-2022 on the study of the water balance of rainfed soybean fields, mainly for 2019, 2021 and 2022, are given. It has been established that the deep layers of the soil (40-150 cm) more consistently reflect the influence of the plant component than the surface ones. During seasons 2019 (134 DAP) and 2022 (147 DAP) the same amount of water (63 ± 1 mm) was lost from the 40-150-cm soil layer by the soybean fields (variety Aura).

The seasonal change in soil moisture reserves in dependence on the genetic form of soybeans was studied. In 2021, water reserves decreased in the 0-150 cm layer: for the Pentata variety - by 103 mm, and for the A 500 line - by 53 mm. Thus, line A 500 (MG I) retained 50 mm more water in the field for the next season compared to variety Pentata (MG III).

Keywords: soybean, soil moisture, maturity group.

Any decrease in non-beneficial water consumption must result in increased production per unit of consumed water [Blum A., Perry C. et al., 2009]. Increasing the efficient water use by cultivated soybean *Glycine max* (L.) Merr. requires an accurate assessment of the moisture reserves of soybean fields in different seasons [Харчук О., 2019]. The aim of the work was - to the end of the vegetation season to determinate the differences in soil water content of soybean cenosis and bare soil in the 0-150 cm soil layer and to assess the influence of soybean maturity group (MG).

The studies were carried out in 2016 -2022 at the fields of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection (IGFPP), in soybean cenoses with traditional cultivation technology ($400 \cdot 10^3$ plants/ha, row spacing 45 cm) with the different maturity group (MG) varieties: Aura and Pentata (MG III), Stefanel (MG II) and soybean genetic line A500 (MG I). To assess meteorological conditions was used the relative precipitation index (*RPI*) - the ratio of precipitation sum for the given period *P* and the long term average for the same period \bar{P} expressed in percent, $RPI = P/\bar{P} \cdot 100\%$; for long period (from quarter to year) are such criteria of *RPI* value: 0-49,9% (extremely dry), 50,0-74,9% (very dry),

75,0-89,9% (dry) and 90,0-110,0% (average) [Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędski L., 2002]. Gravimetric soil moisture samples were taken by hand drill AM-26 at 10-20 cm depth increments to 150 cm deep (both in cenosis and on bare soil). For each horizon, soil samples were taken in triplicate. To determine soil moisture, the samples were dried in an oven at 105 °C to constant weight [Black C, 1965]. Oven, heated and ventilated, capable of maintaining a temperature of 105 ± 2 °C.

Figure 1 (left) shows the difference in soil color of experimental plots depending on the depth of soil sampling.

From Figure 1 it is possible to see that the surface chernozem layer does not exceed 30–40 cm in depth. With an increase in depth of more than 40 cm, the color of the soil becomes lighter. The lightest color is in the 100-150 cm layer, which is more easy in granulometric composition.

To determine the volumetric soil moisture content, the gravimetric data were multiplied by the soil dry bulk density values, obtained experimentally [Вадюнина

Figure 1. Study of the soil of the experimental field: on the left - the color of soil samples from different depths (layer 0-150 cm, samples from different wells); on the right - soil density determination kit (a ramrod with a guide and drill-cylinders with a volume of 100 cm³).

А.Ф., Корчагина З.А., 1986; ISO 11272, 2017]. The method used involved drying and weighting a soil sample, the volume of which is known (core method). Core samples of known volume were taken with a metal sampling tool (Figure 1, on the right). The main components of the apparatus are core sample holders, thin-walled metal cylinders with a volume of 100 cm³, a steel cap for driving into the soil, and a driver. For sampling a core sample holder of known volume press without deflection and compaction into a vertical or horizontal soil surface far enough to fill the sample. Carefully remove the sample holder and its contents to preserve the natural structure, and trim the soil extending beyond each end of the sample holder with a straight-edged knife. The soil sample volume is thus equal to the volume of the sample holder.

In the 0-150 cm layer, three horizons were identified: 0-40 cm with a density of 1.22±0.04 g/cm³, a 40-100 cm layer with a density of 1.41±0.10 g/cm³, and a 100-150 cm layer with a density of 1.13±0.04 g/cm³. Many researchers note that in some soils, at a depth of 40-60 cm, a metamorphic horizon occurs, which is heavier in granulometric composition than the upper

horizons [Теории и методы физики почв (ред. Шейн Е.В. и Карпачевский Л.О.), 2007]. Taking into account the error in determining the bulk density of the soil, the bulk density of the entire layer of 0-150 cm on average can be characterized by the value of 1.26±0.08 g/cm³. Such bulk density is typical for loamy chernozem soils: for example, А.Д. Воронин (1986) for a typical thick chernozem for a layer of 0-150 cm obtained bulk densities in the range of 1.11-1.34 g/cm³. In general, the density of loamy soils is in the range from 1.0-1.1 to 1.3-1.4 g/cm³ [Бондарев А.Г., 1981].

Thus, our data on the density of the studied soils are in good agreement with the known literature data. Soil density data were used by us to calculate volumetric soil moisture from experimental data on gravimetric soil moisture.

It was previously established that the value of moisture reserves in the soil layer 0-150 cm during the spring sowing period are determined by the total amount of precipitation and their relative index (RPI) in the previous period (September-April) of soil water accumulation [Kharchuk, 2022].

According to the total amount of precipitation in the previous period (September-April) of soil water accumulation three (of 7 seasons in investigation) seasons (2018/2019, 2019/2020 and 2021/2022), were atypically dry (180,0 mm, 108,4 mm and 168,0 mm), as evidenced by the comparison of precipitation during this period with average 320 mm (1886-2022). The season 2021 was normal according to the total amount of precipitation in the previous period (September 2020/April 2021) of soil water accumulation (309,0 mm) with high value of precipitation in vegetation (May-August) period (373,4 mm) according as evidenced by the comparison of precipitation during this period with average 235 mm (1886-2022). Soybean is a warm-season crop, and heat has a great influence on the adaptation, yield, and seed quality of soybean [Wen, H. et al., 2022]. The maturity group (MG) system was used to group soybean varieties according to their photothermal response. Soybean has been classified into 13 MGs according to their maturity, which determines their geographical adaptation to different latitudes [Zhang, L.X.

et al., 2007]. Maturity was measured at the date when 95% of the pods turned brown (R8) [Holshouser, D. and B. Taylor, 2022].

≥ 10 °C active accumulated temperature (≥ 10 °C AAT) is important index to quantify the effects of temperature on soybean development [Wen, H. et al., 2022]. AAT refers to the sum of daily active temperature (daily average temperature ≥ 10 °C in a certain period of time or a certain growing season of crops [Jiang, L. et al., 2011]). The required AAT showed an increasing trend from early to late maturity groups; for each increase of 1 (one) MG, AAT could potentially increase by 254.2 °C and the AAT for MG I, MG II, and MG III are 2336-2589, 2590-2843 and 2844-3097 °C [Wen, H. et al., 2022]. For example, average for two years (2021-2022) AAT of soybean line A 500 was 2374 ± 52 °C, that corresponds to MG I. Variety Pentata belongs to MG III. The phenological differences between A 500 and Pentata on various days after planting (DAP) are shown in Figures 2-4.

Figure 2. General view of part of the experimental site in 2021 (09/09/2021, 120 DAP). In the central part - line A500 (MG I, yellow plants). In the lower right and upper left - Pentata variety (MG III, green plants).

Figure 3. The soybean line A 500 (MG I) in 2022 (left - plants 11/08/2022, 118 DAP; on right - pod 10/08/2022, 117 DAP).

Figure 4. The soybean variety *Pentata* (MG III) in 2022 (left – plants 21/08/2022, 127 DAP; on right - pods 20/08/2022, 126 DAP).

On Figure 5 are shown the soil moisture profiles in the 0-150 cm layer, formed in 2019 (Fig. 5, at the top) and 2022 (Fig. 5, at the bottom) by the time of harvest, as for the soybean *Aura* cenosis as for the black fallow plot (without plants).

In different years differences in the moisture content of the surface horizon of 0-40 cm are associated with different precipitation over the last three weeks before harvesting: in 2019 - only 3 mm, and in 2022 - 70

mm. During the growing season the decrease in the total moisture reserves of the deep layers of the soil of the soybean cenosis is mainly associated with plants [Khar-chuk, O., 2022]. Deep horizons reflect the influence of cenosis (primarily plant transpiration) more stable: in both years, a 40-150 cm soil layer lost during the growing season (134 and 147 DAP, respectively) almost the same amount of water: 63.9 mm in 2019 and 62,7 mm in 2022.

Figure 5. The moisture content in the soil of the soybean cenosis (variety Aura) and in bare area during the harvesting period: at the top – in 2019; below – in 2022.

On Figure 6 are shown the soil moisture profiles in the 0-150 cm layer, formed in 2021 by the end of the

season at the fallow plot and for different according maturity soybean cenosis: variety Pentata (MG III) and line a 500 (MG I).

Figure 6. Moisture content in the soil of soybean cenoses of different maturation groups and on a bare plot.

In usual years (2016, 2017, 2018, 2021) in terms of the amount of precipitation for the period of accumulation of soil moisture from September to April (an average 323 ± 10 mm), the total water reserves in the 0-150 cm layer (at the time of sowing) averaged 347 ± 18 mm.

At the beginning of the season, on May 12, 2021, in the black fallow area the moisture reserves of the 0-150 cm layer were 330.7 mm. For the time period from May 12, 2021 (sowing) to September 28, 2021, 367.6 mm of precipitation fell. But in the black fallow area, to the end of the season the moisture reserves of the 0-150 cm layer practically do not changed, consisted 330.0 mm.

At the same time, in the soybean cenosis the soil moisture reserves of the 0-150 cm layer decreased to a different extent for different genetic forms: for the Pentata variety (MG III) by 102.7 mm, for the Stefanel variety (MG II) by 81.6 mm, while for line A 500 (MG I) - only by 53.1 mm. Therefore, in the plot of soybean cenosis line A 500 (MG I) for the next season, 49.6 mm more water was preserved compared with variety Pentata (MG III).

Despite large precipitation (367.6 mm) for the growing season of 2021 due to subsequent insignificant (168.0 mm) precipitation during the period of accumulation of moisture in the soil (September 2021-April 2022), by the time of sowing-2022 the total soil moisture reserves in the 0-150 cm layer amounted to 313.1 mm, while in deep soil layers appeared the moisture deficit relative to the average in usual years (2016-2018, 2021) - in general, minus 43 mm in the 40-150 cm layer. Insufficient precipitation over 8 months of moisture accumulation continued in May and June (21.0 and 6.7 mm, respectively), resulting in severe meteorological drought over 10 months (September 2021-June 2022) with an RPI of 44%. Determination of soil moisture on July 26, 2022 showed that in the Aura soybean cenosis in the entire soil profile of 0-150 cm, the reserves of available moisture were exhausted. The use in the previous year (2021) of a more earlier (MG I) soybean variety could reduce agronomic drought next year (in 2022).

Conclusion

The deep layers of the soil reflect the influence of the plant component more consistently than the surface layers. During seasons 2019 (134 DAP) and 2022 (147 DAP) the same amount of water (63 ± 1 mm) was lost from the 40-150-cm soil layer by the soybean cenosis (variety Aura).

Seasonal change in soil moisture reserves depends on the genetic form of soybean. In 2021, water reserves decreased in the 0-150 cm layer: for the Pentata variety by 103 mm, and for the A 500 line by 53 mm. Thus, line A 500 (MG I) retained 50 mm more water in the field for the next season compared to variety Pentata (MG III).

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